

Examining the Effect of Employee's Social Life on Productivity: A Case Study of Employees in 4- Star Hotel in Ghana

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Abstract

Objective: This study seeks to investigate on the effect of employee's social life on productivity among 4- star hotel employees in Ghana.

Method: A cross-sectional study design was carried out with a sample size of 220 employees of 4-star hotels in Accra, Ghana. Univariate analysis was used to determine the significant difference between variables.

Result: Social Life (SOL) has a statistically significant positive effect on the productivity (PROD) of employees working in the hotel industry. Specifically, SOL has a coefficient of 1.210, which is statistically significant at 1% level. Therefore, a unit change (increase) in SOL will result in a 1.210 change (increase) in the productivity of employees. The p-value (0.000) indicates the hypothesis is statistically significant.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the social life of the employees plays a pivotal role in their productivity. Therefore, ensuring productivity among employees requires that the social life of the employees be improved.

Keywords: hotel, social, life, employees, Ghana, Accra

Introduction

The hotel industry is a service-oriented industry that relies heavily on the behavior and attitudes of employees to provide friendly and courteous services to customers. Manpower in the hotel industry is the most important resource. In an industry where service is highly personalized, guest satisfaction can only be achieved when workers are happy and satisfied with their jobs (1).

Kuntz (2) argues that today a special attention is given to well-being as a business management strategy. Therefore, there is a fundamental change in the employers' perceptions of employee health and its impact on the overall financial welfare of a company. Organisational leaders realize that healthier employees are more efficient, and a real strategic advantage in any organisation is achieved by combining lower health care costs with higher employee productivity. However, to keep employees satisfied and productive, it is necessary to enhance their well-being at work and working conditions.

Unfortunately, work and family conflict is a common problem faced by employees in the hospitality industry due to the nature of the job that needs to be performed in an attempt to satisfy hotel guests at all times (3). The hospitality industry is a labor-

intensive industry, which means that most services rendered in hospitality establishments are based on human efforts. In addition, the times that these employees work are mostly out of the usual working time (8 am to 5 pm). That is, the time when people from other industries are off duty, with weekends and holidays topping the list. The characteristics of hotel work coupled with the culture of Sub-Saharan Africans, especially Ghanaians, make it difficult to successfully combine and manage roles, responsibilities, and duties from both the work and the family domains. The traditional culture of Africans, and more specifically Ghanaians, suggests that women are caregivers while men are the breadwinners. This puts pressure on men and women alike, particularly in dual income earning families, to balance work and family life regardless of the individual's status at the workplace (4) and life-cycle stage. These traditional norms are similar throughout the Sub-Saharan region (5) and make hotel employees more susceptible to WFC and its effects.

Objective

This study seeks to investigate on the effect of employee's social life on productivity among 4- star hotel employees in Ghana.

Hypothesis

H⁰: There is no significant differences between the effects of employee's social life on productivity among 4- star hotel employees in Ghana.

H¹: There is a significant difference between the effects of employee's social life on productivity among 4- star hotel employees in Ghana.

Methods and Materials

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Accra, Ghana, across 29 districts in the Region, located at the southern part of Ghana. Accra, Ghana was selected for the research due to the high rate of hospitality industries in the region. Data was taken at a single point on a specific duration (May 2021 - December 2021).

Sampling

A sample is the representative of the population was selected. Information gathered from the hotels revealed that there are approximately 400 employees (i.e. total number of employees in the selected hotels). Based on the population, suitable sample size was computed using Yamane's formula. Yamane's formula was calculated using a confidence interval of 95% and a precision level (error) of 0.05 (6). The sample size of the study is 220 respondents across 4 star hotels namely; Golden Tuilp, Kempenski, Accra City, Fiesta Royale and La-Palm Royal Beach hotel. A simple random sampling technique was used to ensure that each employee across the 5 (4-star) hotels in Accra had an equal chance of being selected for the study.

Sample Size Recruitment

1. Research officer selected respondents from 5 (4-star) hotels in Accra.
2. Respondents were asked if they could participate in a research study, those who agreed proceeded.
3. Respondents were asked whether they are employees of the hotel, those who were participated and those who were not, were thanked and told they could not participate.
4. Respondents who were proceeded to answer the questionnaire.

Data Collection

Field data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire. Data was collected in English Language and it was a self-structured questionnaire. Questionnaire was designed to answer the study objective. Data collection was done according to the American Psychological Association data collections guidelines and ensured complete anonymity of all data.

Data analysis

Errors were addressed on the day of data collection after checking the completed questionnaires for consistency and completeness. Prior to inputting the data into SPSS version 22, the data was cleaned, sorted, and coded.

The sample population was described using descriptive statistics, which generated frequencies and percentages of the characteristics of respondents who participated in the study. The independent variable is the prevalence of the utilization of dietary supplement and dependent variable is female adults in Accra, Ghana. Using univariate analysis to measure the positive or negative effect on the productivity of employees in the hospitality industry.

Data Analysis Sub-section

Using a univariate analysis, it emerged that, Social Life (SOL) has a statistically significant positive effect on the productivity (PROD) of employees working in the hotel industry. Specifically, SOL has a coefficient of 1.210, which is statistically significant at 1% level. Therefore, a unit change (increase) in SOL will result in a 1.210 change (increase) in the productivity of employees. The p-value (0.000) indicates the hypothesis is statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Regression Results on the Impact of Employee's Social Life on their Productivity.

	Coefficient	Standard Errors	t-stats	Sig.
SOL	1.210	.021	57.701	0.000
Constant	-0.948	.064	-14.888	0.000
Dependent Variable = PROD				
F-statistics = 3329.451		prob>F-stat = 0.000		
R-Squared = 0.972				
Durbin-Watson = 0.080				
VIF= .100				

P value 0.05

Discussion

It was evident from the results as stated in Table 1 that unsocial working hours do affect the social life of employees in the hotel sector. Furthermore, the social life (SOL) of the employees was also found to play a crucial role in productivity (PROD). The coefficient of SOL in a univariate regression analysis between SOL and PROD is 1.210, indicating that a unit increase in SOL will cause PROD to increase by 1.210. Similarly, in the literary work of Tate (7), it also emerged that the social life of the employees plays a pivotal role in their productivity; hence, it is essential to ensure that the social life of the employees is not in a disarray.

It should be noted that the reconciliation of work and private life is a complex phenomenon that depends on both an individual's personal life situation and a situation at work (8). Successful WLB is positively associated with lower turnover, organisational citizenship behaviour, higher work engagement, increased productivity and organisational commitment (9), as well as job satisfaction, life and employee wellbeing (10).

Strengths and limitation

The design of this study is its strongest point; it used a thorough research technique to solve the under-discussed scientific topic. The author would like to draw attention to a drawback notwithstanding the study's satisfactory completion. This kind of study might be prone to response biases. Since this was a self-administered questionnaire, data collection largely depended on the respondents' ability to accurately and truthfully provide information on dietary supplement use. Despite that, I believe that important lessons can be learned from this study. The study provides valuable insights into a field of study that has not been extensively investigated within the Ghanaian context.

Conclusion

The study investigated on the effect of social life of employees in 4-star hotels in Accra, Ghana productivity. The study indicated a statistical significance in the objectives. It also emerged that social life of the employees plays a pivotal role in their productivity. This calls for the need of more social life interventions.

Author Contributions

Emilia Esta Milla-Ameakor contributed to the study concept, design, data acquisition, analysis, interpretation, drafting and final review of manuscript.

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This study did not receive any funding.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares there are no conflict of interest

Ethical Approval and Consent of Participate

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the before data was collected from the participants (.....). All study participants consented for participation in this study. There were no risks in this research and participation was voluntary with freedom to withdraw at any time

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